

A HISTOPATHOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE FOR CARPAL TUNNEL SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT Introduction: Carpal tunnel syndrome(CTS) is the most frequent compressive neuropathy of upper extremity. The median nerve is compressed under flexor retinaculum because of primary or secondary reasons. Although primary CTS may have different causes, idiopathic CTS's aetiology is unclear We aimed to evaluate tenosynovial tissue change under flexor retinaculum as a cause of idiopathic CTS even more as a possible cause of recurrent CTS. **Materials and Methods:** We operated 175 patients with carpal tunnel syndrome who had median nerve compression. 110 patients were diagnosed as idiopathic CTS were included in our study. The same surgeon performed open carpal tunnel release, and synovial samples were taken from synovial connective tissue under the median nerve for pathological examination. **Results:** All patients were followed-up 22 months (12 to 35 months) prospectively. Mean age was 45 years(22 to 65). Preop VAS score was 6 post op VAS score was 1. Synovial hypertrophy was detected at 38 of 110 patients(34%). Other pathological results were; 13 reactive synovitis(11%), 8 ganglion(7.2%), 51 fibrohyaline nodulation(46.3%). **Conclusions:** We recommend the evaluation of tenosynovial tissue under flexor retinaculum after releasing the retinaculum. If there is an inflammation or hypertrophy or a mass effect, the surgeon must do partial tenosynovectomy to decrease the volume of the carpal tunnel and to prevent recurrence.

KEYWORDS Carpal tunnel, mass, median nerve, surgery, synovium

Introduction

Upper extremity compression neuropathies are common than lower extremity and compression of the median nerve at the carpal tunnel is the most common compression neuropathy of upper extremity. Reported prevalence for carpal tunnel syndrome is approximately between 1%-7%. It results in pain and dysesthesia at hand and thus effects the patient's social or working life [1].

Each process that narrow carpal tunnel or increase the pressure inside, may lead to entrapment of the median nerve. Although the aetiology is unclear, the median nerve may compress under flexor retinaculum because of secondary reasons[2] like wrist fractures, metabolic disturbances, rheumatoid arthritis or tumoural mass effects. Aetiology is unclear mostly, and most cases are referred as idiopathic.

Numerous studies are trying to reveal the exact cause of idiopathic carpal tunnel syndrome(CTS). Although investigators tried to find an explanation of the aetiology at histological perspective, exact histological connection with primer or recurrent CTS development is not understood clearly yet. Two – twenty-five percent of patients remain symptomatic or have an early recurrence of symptoms [3]. Although most common pathologic finding reported at reoperation is the incomplete release of the transverse carpal ligament we think that synovium under the median nerve can also be one of the causes. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the tenosynovial change at synovial connective tissue under the median nerve as a possible cause for

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primer CTS even more recurrent CTS.

Material and Methods

We operated 175 patients with carpal tunnel syndrome who had median nerve compression symptoms clinically or only with EMG findings between 2001-2009. The diagnosis was made by investigating typical nerve compression symptoms (numbness in the radial three and one-half digits and tingling in the area of median nerve distribution, pain especially at night) and positive Phalen's and Tinel 's tests. The same experienced neurologists performed all EMG 's.

65 Patients with a history of rheumatic diseases, diabetes mellitus and chronic renal failure or such seconder causes of CTS were excluded. Idiopathic carpal tunnel syndrome was accepted as study inclusion criteria, and 110 patients with no possible explanation were diagnosed as idiopathic CTS were included in our study. All the patients participating in the study were informed about the study. Institutional review board (IRB) approval was not needed.

The same surgeon performed open carpal tunnel release surgeries. The incision was made in line with the space between the middle finger and the ring finger. All operations were made under local anaesthesia. The transverse carpal ligament, distal third of the deep forearm fascia and flexor retinaculum were cut with beware of the distal branches of the palmar cutaneous branch of the median nerve. Median nerve was released, and synovial tissue under the median nerve was assessed. Synovial samples were taken from synovial connective tissue under the median nerve for pathological examination (Figure 1a-b). Specimens fixed in 10% buffered formalin immediately.

Results

One hundred ten patients were included in our study. All patients were followed-up 22 months (12 to 35 months) prospectively. Mean age was 45 years(22 to 65). Eighty patients were women, and 30 were men. We used a VAS score to figure out patients progression at pain relief. All neurological complaints resolved completely. Preop VAS score was 6 post op VAS score was 1.

The diagnosis was made with EMG at 93 patients. Although EMG was normal clinical examination was compatible with nerve compression at 17 patients. Synovial hypertrophy was detected at 38 of 110 patients(34%). Other pathological results were; 13 reactive synovitis(11%) (Figure 2), 8 ganglion(7.2%) (Figure 3), 51 fibrohyaline nodulation(46.3%) (Figure 4).

Discussion

Idiopathic CTS usually occurs because of either a decrease in the size of the carpal canal or an increase in the volume of the contents within the tunnel[2]. At their study, Nakamichi and Lin took a biopsy from transverse carpal ligament to discriminate aetiology but found no differences between the histological characteristics of the flexor retinaculum[4,5] with CTS diagnosed patients and non-CTS patients. This information emphasizes the belief that CTS is caused by an increase in the volume of contents within the carpal tunnel either because of the tenosynovium or hand muscles like lumbrical or superficialis muscle[2,6]. Investigators have started to examine flexor tenosynovium for mass effect. Phalen noted that thickening or fibrosis of the synovial tissue under the nerve within the carpal tunnel is one of the most common causes of the idiopathic CTS[7-11]. Hulsizer, Gross and

Figure 1A: Synovial hypertrophy.

Figure 1B: Synovectomy sample.

Figure 2: Reactive synovitis.

Figure 3: Ganglion.

Figure 4: Fibrohyaline nodulation.

Neal's histological studies showed nonspecific fibrous changes and oedema [8,12-14] at flexor tenosynovium of CTS patient's. Shum tried to explain correlation with the histologic appearance and the gross appearance of the flexor tenosynovium with CTS and assessed the role of flexor tenosynovectomy by clinical outcome[2]. In his study, he revealed that flexor tenosynovectomy compared with sectioning of the ligament alone provided no additional benefit in terms of clinical outcome. Histopathological examination demonstrated the absence of acute or chronic inflammation or any fibroblastic proliferation. In his report's light, many authors don't check the tenosynovial tissue under the nerve, except the patient under dialysis treatment or have diabetes, rheumatological disease. Botte and Von Schroeder reported that tenosynovectomy indicated only for proliferative tenosynovitis (rheumatoid arthritis, gout and granulomatous infection), bacterial or fungal infection, or markedly thickened tenosynovium because of amyloid deposition at dialysis patients[15,16]. In our series we excluded the patients under dialysis treatment or diabetes mellitus and who had rheumatological history. Our results showed that nearly 34% of the patients have synovial hypertrophy as the cause of CTS. This result is higher than the current literature.

Many authors tried to find the cause of recurrent CTS [2,17,18]. Schelle reported that the most common reason for persistent complaints after CTS surgery is an incomplete release of the flexor retinaculum [19]. Campagna made wrist MRI assessment for recurrent CTS after open release and revealed synovial mass effect as 9 cases of 35. Nerve compression clinic was because of 3 synovial cysts, three accessory muscle and three tenosynovitis [20]. We hypothesize that synovial hypertrophy, which we found at a high rate of 34%, may be responsible for recurrent CTS cases. It is necessary to organize another prospective study to confirm this hypothesis.

The low rate of mass effect may explain the absence of a significant difference of this feature between the recurrent CTS and control groups that were not a truly disease-free. Because; the control group had undergone MRI for suspicion of ulnar nerve entrapment in the Guyon's tunnel. Stütz reported incidence for tumoral mass in carpal tunnel as 2%. Kang reported that in cases with swelling or tenderness on the area of wrist flexor creases, it is essential to obtain further radiological investigation to rule out space-occupying lesions around the carpal tunnel [3,21]. Because of the low mass rate and cost effectivity, we did not recommend MRI evaluation before the primary surgery, but surgeons should take in mind the mass effects at suspected diagnosis of the primary or recurrent CTS.

We recommend the evaluation of tenosynovial tissue after releasing the flexor retinaculum. If it is inflamed and there is hypertrophy or mass effect, the surgeon must do partial tenosynovectomy to decrease the volume of the carpal tunnel and so can prevent the high recurrence rate. A better understanding of the causes of CTS may lead us new surgical interventions and decrease the recurrence rate.

Competing Interests

There were no financial supports or relationships between authors and any organization or professional bodies that could pose any conflict of interest.

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